

WORKING WITH A TEXTBOOK IN BIOLOGY LESSONS

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Abstract. *In this article, the content of biological science at school is reflected in the textbook, which is one of the important sources of knowledge and a means of teaching students. Since the textbook use system is part of the general system of the educational process in the lesson, it reflects the learning goals, the possibilities of the content of biology textbooks, the specifics of individual topics and their connection with teacher training, while the system reflects the place of the textbook at the present stage and its role in the learning process.*

Keywords: *textbook, groups, formation, biological knowledge, learning skills, positive attitudes, self-education.*

Currently, the issue of educating a student as a comprehensively developed personality is very acute. In this regard, biological literacy of school students becomes necessary. The tasks facing school biological education are implemented through curricula and textbooks developed on the basis of standards approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of Uzbekistan.

The content of the school biology subject is reflected in the textbook, which is one of the important sources of knowledge and a means of teaching students. Since the textbook use system is part of the general system of the educational process in the classroom, the possibilities of the content of biology textbooks, the specifics of individual topics and the teacher's preparedness are determined by the learning objectives. At the same time, the system reflects the place of the textbook and its role in the educational process at the present stage. The textbook is a system-forming component of the educational and methodological complex of the subject of biology.

When organizing students' work with various structural components of the textbook, three groups of techniques are distinguished:

Group 1 - techniques for working with the orientation apparatus in the textbook content: introduction, table of contents, symbols for tasks, instructions on how to use the textbook.

Mastering the techniques of the first group involves the development of students' skills to navigate in a textbook, quickly find the necessary material in the text, and memorize the main thing from the main text. These skills are "organizational", as they are used to organize the attention and learning activities of students.

Group 2 - techniques for working with text;

The techniques are used when students study textbook texts in the process of acquiring biological knowledge and fostering positive attitudes towards nature by analyzing, comparing, classifying the studied material, establishing cause-and-effect relationships and evidence from the text, evaluating the text for completeness of content, etc. The formed skills of this group are called "intellectual", contributing to the development of mental activity of students.

Group 3 - methods of working with the apparatus for mastering educational material and organizing students' educational activities: questions, assignments, illustrations, instructions for practical work.

The assimilation of the techniques of the third group is aimed at the formation of practical skills among schoolchildren - to be able to independently perform practical work according to the

instructions of the textbook, prepare experience for demonstration, find the answer to a question, make diagrams, tables, use drawings. The skills of this group are conventionally called "practical".

In the learning process, such techniques of working with a textbook should be used that implement the basic functions of the textbook (teaching, educating and developing) and contribute to the formation of biological knowledge, educational skills and positive attitudes towards nature among students; are aimed at developing independence in obtaining knowledge; provide a close connection between mental and specific practical educational activities; introduce students to self-education.

Let's consider as an example such a methodical technique as working with the text of a textbook. This technique is understood as reading the text of a textbook aloud, followed by commenting or answering questions from the teacher. This technique is most actively used in elementary school when teaching children to read and understand text; in middle and high school it is used less often, although its effectiveness is very high.

This technique of working with the text of the textbook should be used at least once in each topic. This is due to two features of modern schoolchildren.

Firstly, they read very little and the reading speed is low. The speed of reading aloud in a tenth grader is comparable to the reading speed of a 5th-6th grade student, while the volume of proposals for studying information by the senior grade increases 2.5 times. Thus, there is a contradiction between the requirements of education and the capabilities of schoolchildren.

Secondly, biological language contains a large number of specific terms that are difficult not only to understand, but also just to pronounce aloud.

Reading aloud in the lesson allows you to identify students for whom this skill is a clear difficulty.

In addition, the teacher has the opportunity to manage the process of learning knowledge and organize the development of a correct understanding of biological terms.

The first stage in such work is the reception of listening, reading aloud in the classroom, followed by a comment by the teacher or students. When reading aloud, the teacher, in the process of commenting, formulates the main idea.

The second stage in such work is the technique of asking questions on the text. This work allows you to identify the understanding of what students have read, as well as the formation of such skills as identifying the main and secondary. First, students should make up the maximum number of questions on the text, then divide them into two groups: those asking about the main and secondary. Such work allows you to form the ability to highlight the main thoughts in the text.

You can also suggest comparing the questions posed by the students themselves with the questions placed at the end of the paragraph. This allows you to link the text of the paragraph with the questions after it, to show the importance of these questions for identifying the main thoughts.

The third stage is the method of highlighting the main idea in an affirmative form (thesis). The thesis is a briefly formulated main provisions of the text, a concise statement of the main ideas of the text, which incorporate the essential in the educational material. That is, there is a logical transition from one form of working with the text – asking questions to another – a thesis summary.

Learning how to use a textbook begins in elementary school. In botany lessons, it is necessary to continue the formation, since the development of this skill allows you to reduce the time for students to complete homework. The most effective use of the texts of the botany textbook is to consolidate the teacher's explanation, and if the material allows, then studying new material.

Here you can offer work with illustrations to consolidate students' knowledge, you can give a task: to find in the text the material necessary to answer a certain question that allows you to reveal a particular concept.

Independent work on the topic "Rules for watering plants" is carried out according to the textbook after explaining the material. The assignment questions orient students not to specify the rules, but to explain them.

Task: Read the article "Root absorption of water" in the textbook and answer the questions:

1. Why is it better to water vegetable and flower plants in the evening?
2. Why is it necessary to water indoor plants?
3. Why should plants not be watered with cold water?

The textbook can be used to summarize and verify knowledge, bring it into the system.

For example, the test work on the topic "Flowers and fruit" allows students to find out about the structure and biological knowledge of the main parts of the flower, about the processes of pollination and fertilization, fruit and seed formation. Here you can give a task on the options. For example, the task: choosing a variant.

1. For what purpose is pasticalation of plants used in agriculture?
2. Why should grass be mowed for hay at the beginning of its flowering?
3. Solve the problem: during the flowering of the apple trees, the weather was rainy. Why did this upset the gardeners?

The content of the botany course is of great importance for students to learn how to draw up diagrams and tables based on working with text. Such work helps to bring disparate facts into the system, allows to highlight the main thing. In the case when I do not have the opportunity to show experience, I conduct independent work with the textbook drawing, defining it by the task.

1. Consider the drawing showing that plant growth depends on the supply of nutrients in the cotyledons and explain the experience.

2. You will conclude why it is necessary to take large seeds for sowing.

A similar work can be done when explaining the material about leaf arrangement. Independent work with the drawing can also take place when checking knowledge. The drawings help to check the depth of assimilation of concepts and are of a searching nature.

For example, consider the drawing "Comparative root length of cultivated plants" and find out which of these plants have the longest root system and which have the smallest. Which plants will therefore need more fertile soil? Which of these plants will be able to tolerate drought and why?

When teaching zoology, students should master the ability to navigate in a textbook with the help of a table of contents, use a preface, an index of basic terms, draw up a plan of the studied material, verbally state the main content of the paragraph, use drawings as illustrations to the text, find in it the material necessary to answer the question. A descriptive text is often found in a zoology textbook - this has a positive effect on the development of cognitive independence. It is simpler and more accessible for students. Therefore, in my lessons I often use independent work with words written in italics according to the assignment.

1. You write or find words written in italics.
2. Verbally explain their meaning.
3. Teach to pronounce them correctly and remember how to spell them correctly.

Finding answers to questions in the text, making plans for a paragraph or its individual parts, filling out tables and diagrams in the text, searching for questions, working on the text using drawings. An example based on a textbook drawing, tell us about the nutrition and development of an ordinary amoeba.

1. Based on the textbook drawing, tell us about the nutrition and development of an ordinary amoeba.

2. Using the drawing, tell us about the features of the location of the green euglena. Comparison, analysis, generalization and conclusions, in which the results of the work of skills have become an integral part of the zoology lesson.

It is impossible to occupy a significant place in the anatomy lessons of this work. Syllabic course material is needed in a good explanation by the teacher using clarity, but to study certain simple questions, close knowledge and exercises of students in the skills to work with a book, it is advisable to organize independent work with text, drawings, diagrams, textbook questions. A modern subject program requires students to be able to draw up a paragraph plan, present its content, use risks and find answers to questions.

To do this, it is necessary to steal various kinds of tasks that direct the student's thoughts to highlight the main essence in the available material. For example, if there are similarities and differences in the structure of the human and animal skeletons, the teacher can do such work.

Task.

1. Consider the drawing in the text of the textbook. Establish similarities and differences in the structure of humans, monkeys and dogs.

2. Establish the features of the difference in the structure of the human and animal foot.

3. Find the differences in the structure of the human and animal skulls.

Independent work can be carried out according to the paragraphs, which set out the sanitary and hygienic rules for the tasks:

1. Make hygiene rules in a notebook.

2. Using the textbook material, give an anatomical and physiological explanation of these rules. Work with illustrations and tables, although limited, but still small independent work can be carried out either in the classroom or while doing homework. When repeating the studied topics, I use programmed dictation, for example, on the topics "Blood", "Blood circulation" and "Digestion".

Independent work of students with a textbook acquires a specific weight in the study of general biology. The creative use of the textbook in all lessons helps students to understand the educational material more deeply, to understand a particular issue. But the method of independent work with a textbook in high school has its own characteristics. In high school, it is advisable to practice the state of the abstract of an article or paragraph, writing annotations, disclosing definitions, drawing conclusions, finding evidence, etc.

In teaching practice, I most often use tasks of a general nature. However, tasks that direct the cognitive activity of students to assimilate a certain range of issues and develop thinking are more effective. For example, in the lesson "Species and its criteria", the main task is for students to learn the modern definition of a species, clearly know the characteristics of each criterion, the need for their joint use in determining the species. Such a task will help you here. Task:

1. Read the text of the paragraph, expand the content of the definition of the type.

2. Make a brief description of the criteria of the type, illustrate it with examples.

It is known that monotonous work tires students, reduces interest in learning, so it is necessary to diversify the tasks and forms of work with the textbook. Filling out and compiling tables have a great effect in mastering the material. For example, when studying the topic "Structure and functions of the cell", I suggest that students fill out the table "Mitochondria", "Plastids" using the text of the textbook.

Task: Read the text about mitochondria and plastids, make a table in which you specify the relationship of structure with functions.

Example of a task:

Students need to read the text and make certain notes in it according to their knowledge and understanding. I supplement the work with a task - to compose questions that expand knowledge (there are no direct answers to these questions in the text and require additional information), as well as problematic questions. I conduct contests for the best question of the 2nd and 3rd categories.

Such a method as independent work with a textbook can be reproductive. But provided that students independently, without the participation of a teacher, read the text according to his assignment and transform it into a plan, diagram, table, and other forms of writing in notebooks, this method becomes active, since this work involves mental operations of analysis and synthesis, comparison, highlighting the main thing, concretization and generalization, it is effectively activates and develops students' logical thinking. This allows you to differentiate work with students, to combine individual, group and frontal forms of organization of educational activities.

1) The nervous system acts as an integrative system, linking sensitivity, motor activity and the work of other regulatory systems (endocrine and immune) into one whole. The nervous system is divided into two types — central and peripheral.

The brain and spinal cord belong to the central nervous system, and all nerves and nerve endings, nodes and nerve plexuses that permeate the body belong to the peripheral nervous system. The central nervous system regulates the activity of all organs and tissues, transmits operational information to the body about changes in conditions – external and internal, analyzes the nature and strength of irritation and carries out responses, while correcting the work of the endocrine, cardiovascular, musculoskeletal, respiratory and other systems.

The peripheral nervous system acts as a conductor between them, although it is located outside the brain and spinal cord. Due to its functions, it is divided into the somatic and autonomic nervous system.

The somatic nervous system covers the entire skin and musculoskeletal system, while providing sensory and motor functions.

The autonomic nervous system is responsible for the activity of the glands of external and internal secretion, internal organs, the state of the lymphatic and circulatory systems. Its functions extend to the provision of respiration, blood circulation, digestion, reproduction, substances in the body and its growth as a whole.

A. Using the information in the text, make a diagram:

B. Analyze the information in the text and write 5 questions to it, which would begin with the words "Why?"

2) Food with a high content of plant fibers, trace elements and vitamins eliminates the development of diseases such as heart attack, stroke, hypertension, diabetes mellitus and cancer and significantly increases life expectancy. The proportion of foods with high bioenergetic

properties (raw vegetables, herbs, fruits, berries, sprouted grains, nuts, seeds, honey, unpolished cereals with minimal heat treatment) should be increased in the diet, and preferably in natural form and daily. It is better not to consume carbohydrate and protein foods, starches and sweets at the same time, especially for people with digestive diseases.

A. The diet of all people should include enough raw vegetables and fruits. Why?

B. Vitamins are not the building and energy material of our body, but they must be included in the human diet. Why?

Thus, the ultimate goal of using a textbook in the classroom is to prepare students for self-education through the ability to work with a textbook and use these skills when working with other literature, organizing their education process to achieve goals, as well as to form students' personal relationships to the process of cognition by realizing its "meaning" for the individual.

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